

Synthesis of Complexes of 2-(Benzothiazolyl-2'-aminoimino)-1,2-diphenylethanone with some Bivalent Transition Metal Ions

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Literature survey reveals that though numerous work has been done with hydrazone derivatives as ligands, the ligational behaviour of hydrazone of benzil containing benzothiazole moiety such as 2-(benzothiazolyl-2'-aminoimino)-1,2-diphenylethanone (Hbaide) has not yet been studied. In continuation of our work¹ on hydrazone derivatives containing heterocyclic ring as a part of the ligand moiety, the present investigation deals with the synthesis of complexes of bivalent Co, Ni, Cu, Mn and Zn with the above titled ligand.

Results and Discussion

The analytical and molar conductance data of the complexes (Table 1) support the suggested formulae. The electronic spectrum of the ligand reveals three bands near 27 174, 29 070 and 37 313 cm^{-1} , which may be assigned to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transitions with extended conjugation. However, the spectra of the metal complexes were not studied in the above region as the study in this region is less informative because of intra-ligand transitions and bands of the type $L \rightarrow M$ or $M \rightarrow L$.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Metal%: Found/ (Calcd.)	Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ mol^{-1}
Hbaide	Yellow	120	—	—
[Cu(baide) ₂].3H ₂ O	Violet	>250	7.60 (7.60)	12.9
[Co(baide) ₂].2H ₂ O	Grey	>250	7.22 (7.29)	14.8
[Ni(baide) ₂].2H ₂ O	Brown	>250	7.16 (7.19)	16.5
[Mn(baide) ₂].3H ₂ O	Brown	>250	6.71 (6.65)	13.9
[Zn(baide) ₂].3H ₂ O	Lovoytint	>250	7.89 (7.82)	15.6

The nmr spectrum of the ligand showed a complex multiplet at δ 7.2–7.9 corresponding to 14 aromatic protons of the three phenyl groups and one proton of the secondary amino group.

The ligand revealed characteristic ir bands² at \sim 3 100 (NH), \sim 2 910 (CH phenyl), \sim 1 710 (C=O), \sim 1 590 (C=N), \sim 1 220 (C–N exocyclic) and \sim 1 050 cm^{-1} (N–N). Besides,

a multiple band system of medium intensity was observed at \sim 1 640 (C–C), 1 540 (C=N cyclic), 1 360 (C–N cyclic) and 750 cm^{-1} (C–S–C) which may be due to ring stretching vibrational mode of benzothiazole moiety³. The most notable feature of the spectra of the complexes is the absence of ligand band due to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and appearance of two new bands of medium intensity at 1 580 (C=C) and 1 530 cm^{-1} (C–O), indicating that the ligand coordinates to the metal ion through deprotonation of enolic OH after enolisation via tautomerisation⁴. Consequently, the bands due to azomethine $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{N=N}}$ of the ligand were absent and a

new band appeared at 1 560 cm^{-1} (–N=N–), indicating thereby coordination of one of the nitrogen atoms of the azo group with the metal ion. This is supported by the disappearance of band at 3 100 cm^{-1} (N–H). The position of band due to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (cyclic), $\nu_{\text{C=C}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C–N}}$ (cyclic) remains practically unaltered in the complexes, indicating non-coordination of ring nitrogen atom to the metal ions, whereas the position of $\nu_{\text{C–S–C}}$ band shifted to lower frequency by 10–20 cm^{-1} in all the complexes, indicating coordination of ring sulphur atom to the metal ion. Besides, a broad band at 3 600 cm^{-1} is observed in all the complexes indicating the presence of lattice water, as evidenced from the absence of band due to rocking mode of vibration. This has also been confirmed by thermal analysis. The coordination through oxygen and nitrogen atoms of the ligand is further confirmed⁶ by the occurrence of new bands at 530–515 (M–O) and 460–450 cm^{-1} (M–N). However, the $\nu_{\text{M–S}}$ band was not studied due to instrumental limitations.

The thermogram of all the complexes exhibit an identical pattern of decomposition. The first weight-loss was encountered at near 90°. The weight-loss corresponds to two water molecules in case of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} and three water molecules in case of Cu^{II}, Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes, indicating them to be lattice water. This is supported by

occurrence of an endothermic peak corresponding to the same temperature of water-loss. The anhydrous complex remained stable up to $\sim 310^\circ$ after which it showed rapid degradation presumably due to decomposition of organic constituents as indicated by the steep fall in the percentage weight-loss. This was followed by an endothermic peak corresponding to the temperature of decomposition. The decomposition continued up to $\sim 450^\circ$ and reached to a stable product in each complex. This corresponds to the composition of their stable oxides.

The room temperature μ_{eff} values of 1.84, 4.9, 3.2 and 5.86 B.M. for the Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes respectively, are in agreement with their octahedral geometry⁷.

The electronic spectrum of the Co^{II} complex showed band at 9 640, 19 900 and 20 640 cm^{-1} , arising due to octahedral field transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(v_1)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(v_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(v_3)$ respectively⁸. The values of transition ratio v_2/v_1 , Dq , B and β as calculated by known method⁸ were found to be 2.06, 1 110 cm^{-1} , 793.8 cm^{-1} and 0.82 respectively. Electronic spectrum of the Ni^{II} complex is consistent with tetragonal geometry showing bands at ~ 8 800, ~ 10 400, 15 600 and 24 400 cm^{-1} assignable to transitions ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$, ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(v_3)$ respectively⁸. The various tetragonal parameters such as D , D_q^E , and D_q^A as calculated by known method⁹ were found to be 182.8, 10 450 and 715 cm^{-1} respectively. The electronic spectra of the Mn^{II} complex displayed band at 17 400, 25 300 and 28 000 cm^{-1} assignable due to transitions ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4E_g(D) + {}^4E_g(G)$ respectively, under an octahedral field around Mn^{II} ion⁸. The various crystal field parameters such as Dq , B , C , F_2 and F_4 calculated following the standard method are 489.7, 385.7, 1311.3, 573, 37.46 cm^{-1} respectively. The Cu^{II} complex showed a broad asymmetric ligand field band at 14 000–15 000 cm^{-1} along with a CT band at 26 000 dm^{-1} . The former band can be assigned to the transition ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ in a distorted octahedral field under D_{4h} symmetry.

The esr spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex exhibited well-resolved anisotropic signals in parallel and perpendicular ${}^{63}\text{Cu}$ region. The magnetic and bonding parameters deduced from the spectra are $g_{\parallel} = 2.32$, $g_{\perp} = 2.08$, $g_{\text{av}} = 2.185$, $A_{\parallel} = 185$, $A_{\perp} = 107.5$ and $A_{\text{av}} = 115.53$. The covalency parameter α^2 as calculated from g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} and A_{\parallel} values was found to be 0.92. The observed data show that g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values are closer to 2 and $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$. This suggests major distortion in the Cu^{II} complexes from Oh symmetry. The α^2 value for this complex is commensurate with considerable covalent character in σ -bonding involving metal ion and ligand⁹.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of A.R. grade. 2-Hydrazinobenzothiazole was prepared¹⁰ by refluxing ethanolic solution of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole with hydrazinhydrate. The hydrazone (Hbaide) was obtained as yellow solid by refluxing the hydrazine with benzil in 1 : 1 molar ratio in ethanol. The complexes were prepared by refluxing the hydrated metal(II) chloride with the hydrazone in ethanol in 1 : 2 molar ratio in the pH range 8.0–8.5. The precipitated complexes were washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure over fused CaCl_2 .

C, H and N were analysed by standard method. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrometer, electronic spectra (EtOH for ligand and DMSO for complex) on Shimadzu 180 and Carl-Zeiss-Jena spectrophotometers and ${}^1\text{H}$ nmr spectra (CHCl_3) a Em-390 spectrometer (90 MHz) using tetramethylsilane as the internal standard. The conductance was measured on a Toshniwal CL 01-06 conductivity bridge using 1×10^{-3} M DMF solutions of the complexes. Thermogravimetric analysis was performed on a Netzsch-429 instrument by heating the complexes in air at a rate of 10°min^{-1} . The magnetic moment was measured by the Gouy method at room temperature using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as the calibrant. ESR spectra of Cu^{II} complex were recorded in solid state on a Varian Associate spectrophotometer using 100 kHz, X-band (RT) and field set 3200 gauss.

References

1. D. C. DASH, R. K. BEHERA and M. SEN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 664.
2. K. C. SATPATHY, A. K. PANDA, R. MISHRA and A. MAHAPATRA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1992, **22**, 201.
3. D. C. DASH, F. MEHER and P. C. MOHANTY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **33**, 934.
4. A. K. PANDA, S. ROUT and H. MOHANTY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **33**, 788.
5. B. P. MISHRA, B. B. MAHAPATRA and S. GURU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 832.
6. K. NAKAMATO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1963.
7. B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **154**, 197.
8. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, New York, 1968.
9. B. SINGH, PREETI SRIVASTVA and A. K. SRIVASTVA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1992, **22**, 229.
10. M. SEN, Ph.D. Thesis, Sambalpur University, 1993.